

Personal Data Management Laws and Regulations

What qualifies as personal data? What are you (not) allowed to do with it? Does your research project involve personal data? Do you know how to handle and store it?

Any researcher working with personal data is subject to (Swiss) data protection law and needs to be aware of the relevant laws and regulations.

What is personal data?

Personal data is any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (data subject). There are different categories of personal data:

Ordinary personal data:	Sensitive personal data:
<p>Personal data is information referring to a definite or definable natural person. Examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Name• Date of birth• Email address• Phone number• Sex• Information about particularly characteristic features, e.g. "only woman working in a certain team"	<p>Personal data which are particularly sensitive in relation to fundamental rights and freedoms, which include but are not restricted to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Political, religious or philosophical beliefs• Trade union-related views or activities• Health• Sexual life and/or sexual orientation• Processing of genetic and/or biometric data• Data of vulnerable persons, e.g. children, ethnic minorities etc.

Key laws

The Law on Information and Data Protection of the Canton of Basel-Stadt ([IDG-BS](#)), the Swiss Federal Act on Data Protection ([FADP](#)) and the General Data Protection Regulation of the European Union ([GDPR](#)) protect privacy and regulate the handling of personal data.

The Human Research Act ([HRA](#)) protects the dignity, privacy and health of human beings involved in research concerning human diseases and the structure and function of the human body.

Which law applies when you process personal data?

- Research at the University of Basel: In general, the Cantonal Law on Information and Data Protection ([IDG-BS](#)) and the [Ordinance](#) to the IDG-BS apply to public bodies of the Canton of Basel-Stadt and its municipalities (e.g. University of Basel).
- Private Research and Research at the ETHZ/EPFL: In general, the Swiss Federal Act on Data Protection ([FADP](#)) and the [Ordinance](#) to the FADP apply to private persons and federal bodies (e.g. ETHZ).
- Cross-cantonal research: When processing personal data, the data protection law of the canton where the processing occurs (e.g. collection, storage, revision, or disclosure) typically applies. This means that, in cases involving multiple locations, more than one cantonal data protection law may apply.
- Research with an international dimension:
 - Often the data protection law at the foreign research location is also applicable.
 - If you process personal data of EU individuals or monitor the online behavior of users based in the EU, [GDPR](#) is applicable.

Data and information classification

In order to ensure the confidentiality and security of sensitive data, the [directive on data and information classification of the University of Basel](#) (in German) defines four protection classes and, in this context, also the responsibilities for handling sensitive data. Find more information on data and information classification on the [Intranet of the University of Basel](#).

For more information on data protection at the University of Basel, visit the [Data Protection Office](#) or contact the Data Protection Officer (DPO): datenschutz@unibas.ch.

If you have questions about data and information classification, contact datenklassen@unibas.ch.

